

EFFECTS OF MATRIX MATERIAL AND LAMINATION PARAMETERS ON VORTEX-INDUCED VIBRATION (VIV) OF DEEPWATER COMPOSITE RISERS

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SUMMARY: Vortex-induced vibration (VIV) of composite risers in deepwater petroleum exploration and production (E&P) operations is studied in this paper. The VIV is recognized to be associated with transverse lift forces on the risers caused by periodical shedding of vortices. As the vortex-shedding frequency approaches the riser structural natural frequency, significant transverse oscillation of the riser may occur, leading to fatigue damage and failure. With light-weight composite risers, reduced top tension and lateral structural stiffness of the riser string may be expected. From a structural-dynamics point of view, large transverse and vertical displacements and bending stresses may occur in the riser under platform motion and hydrodynamic loading. The vortex-induced vibration may increase fluid-structure drag forces, affect static equilibrium and dynamic motions, and cause seriously fatigue problems in the riser.

Polymer-matrix composites generally have an inherent damping capacity which is significantly higher than that of conventional steel. Thus the riser dynamics may be controlled by introducing high damping materials in the composite and also by selecting a suitable polymer liner for the riser body structure. The energy dissipation in the composite riser is expected to actively offset the dynamic deformation and bending stress caused by current, waves and vortex-induced loading, and at the same time, alter the basic dynamic motion characteristics of the riser. In this paper, effects of resin matrix viscoelastic dissipation, various liner materials, and laminate lay-up parameters on VIV dynamic responses of composite risers have been investigated. Numerical results have been obtained for the VIV characteristics of a composite riser in a 3,000-ft tension-leg platform (TLP). The high-damping resin matrix used for constructing a composite rigid riser is found to effectively reduce RMS stresses in riser joints. By changing the lamination lay-up with increasing the hoop ply angle or the helical carbon ply angle will reduce the riser VIV stresses. By adding a liner can also reduce the RMS stresses in the riser joint.

KEYWORDS: Vortex-induced vibration, composite risers, polymer viscoelastic properties, damping of polymer composite, liners.

1. INTRODUCTION

Recent advances of lightweight, high-strength, corrosion-resistant composite riser technology [1, 2] provide attractive enabling capability and significant cost savings for deepwater production operations. At present most research and development work on composite risers has focused on manufacturing [3], material design [4], static failure evaluation [5, 6] and riser connector integrity [7]. However, fundamental, but also critical, issues on dynamic responses of composite risers, especially the vortex-induced vibration (VIV), in deepwater E & P systems and environments remain unexplored.

The issue of VIV of offshore marine risers has received a significant amount of attention [8, 9] in the last few years. The VIV is recognized [10, 11] to be associated with transverse lift forces on the risers, which are dynamic and hydroelastic in nature. The hydrodynamic forces, caused by periodical shedding of vortices, are governed by riser structural stiffness and geometry. As the vortex-shedding frequency

approaches, or is coincident with, the riser structural natural frequency, significant transverse oscillations of the risers may occur. Reduced top tension is expected on a composite riser due to weight reduction, and the lateral structural stiffness of the riser string may also be reduced. This could result in large transverse and vertical displacements and bending stresses in the composite riser under platform motion and hydrodynamic loading. The VIV may increase fluid-structure drag forces, affect static equilibrium and dynamic motions, and cause seriously fatigue damage and failure of the risers.

Polymer-matrix composites generally have an inherent damping capacity which is significantly higher [12] than that of conventional steel. Thus the complex composite riser dynamics may be controlled by introducing high damping materials in the composite, and also by selecting a suitable polymer liner for the riser body structure. The energy dissipation in a composite riser is expected to actively offset the dynamic deformation and bending stress caused by current, waves and vortex-induced loading, and at the same time, alter the basic dynamic motion characteristics of the riser. Equally important, proper introduction of the inherent composite damping together with suitable anisotropic material, structural and lamination tailoring will present the most unique opportunities in optimal design and construction of large composite riser structures to meet the stringent dynamics and strength requirements for advanced riser systems.

2. THEORETICAL DEVELOPMENT

2.1 Viscoelastic Composite Riser Structural Stiffness and Riser Structural Damping - Consider a resin (e.g., epoxy) matrix of a polymer composite in the context of polymer viscoelasticity. Dynamic-mechanical properties of the resin matrix can be expressed by the following commonly used complex-modulus representation: $G(\omega) = G_1 + i G_2$, where the real part, G_1 , is the in-phase, (elastic) storage modulus, and the imaginary part, G_2 , is the out-of-phase loss modulus [for material dissipation (and damping)]. The time-domain stress-relaxation modulus (or creep compliance) $G_m(t)$ of the resin matrix used in micromechanics formulation of riser composite viscoelastic material constitutive equations can be obtained mathematically through a Fourier transformation of $G(\omega)$ [13].

For a commonly used structural epoxy in a fiber-reinforced composite riser system, a general representation for $G_m(t)$ has been shown [13] to have the following series form, based on thermodynamic considerations:

$$G_m(t) = G_{m0} \left[1 - \sum_{i=1}^n g_{mi} (1 - e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_{mi}}}) \right], \quad (1)$$

where G_{m0} is the resin elastic modulus, and g_{mi} is the coefficient corresponding to the i -th relaxation time τ_{mi} determined from experiments. The time-dependent viscoelastic properties of a polymer liner can be expressed in a similar form but with different coefficients and relaxation times.

Following Schapery's thermodynamic formulation [14], polymer-matrix viscoelastic constitutive equations can be fully established for a composite (lamina) system. In the current study, both glass and carbon fibers used in hybrid composite riser laminates are assumed to be purely elastic. Including the time-dependent viscoelastic constitutive properties of the polymer composite, one can express the extensional and bending structural stiffnesses of a composite riser cylinder in the forms [15], for example, as:

$$(\tilde{A}_{11})^{\text{visco}} = (\tilde{A}_{11})_0 - \sum_{i=1}^n (\tilde{A}_{11})_i (1 - e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_i}}) \quad (2a) \quad (\tilde{D}_{11})^{\text{visco}} = (\tilde{D}_{11})_0 - \sum_{i=1}^n (\tilde{D}_{11})_i (1 - e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_i}}) \quad (2b)$$

where $(\tilde{A}_{11})_0$ and $(\tilde{D}_{11})_0$ are instantaneous extensional and bending stiffnesses of the composite riser

cylinder, respectively. The extensional structural stiffness (\tilde{A}_{11}) and transverse bending stiffness (\tilde{D}_{11}) of a composite laminate riser cylinder can be obtained through a ply-by-ply CLT formulation [16,17].

2.2. Governing Equations for Composite Riser Dynamics with Viscoelastic Constitutive Equations -

Since the linear dimensions of a cross section area of a composite riser cylinder are assumed to be small compared to its length, a hollow-tube model is used for the composite riser body with the equivalent (extensional and bending) structural stiffnesses given in Eqs. (2a) and (2b). If one refers the composite riser cylinder in an x-y-z structural coordinate system with the z coordinate along the riser axis, the equations of motion for the composite riser may be written as

$$\rho A \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2} \int_{-\infty}^t D_{zz}(t-\tau) \frac{d}{d\tau} \left(\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial z^2} \right) d\tau = F_x, \quad (3a)$$

$$\rho A \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial t^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2} \int_{-\infty}^t D_{zz}(t-\tau) \frac{d}{d\tau} \left(\frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial z^2} \right) d\tau = F_y, \quad (3b)$$

Fig. 1 Composite Riser Cylinder under Current and Wave Loading.

where u and v are displacements along the x and y directions, respectively. F_x and F_y in Eqs. (3a) and (3b) are external dynamic loading. A number of theoretical, experimental and empirical models [18] are available in the literature to account for the forces caused by waves and currents.

For a vertical composite riser cylinder, the force per unit length in the direction of wave motion (x -direction) and vortex shedding (y -direction) may be written as

$$F_x = C_m \rho \frac{\pi D^2}{4} \frac{dU}{dt} + \frac{1}{2} C_D \rho D |U| U, \quad (4a)$$

$$F_y = \frac{1}{2} \rho C_L D U^2 \cos(2\pi f_s t) \quad (4b)$$

where C_m , C_D and C_L are the inertia, drag (fluid damping) and lift coefficient, respectively. The D is the riser cylinder diameter; ρ , the fluid density, and U , the water particle velocity in the direction of wave motion. dU/dt is the derivative of velocity with respect to time.

The force F_x is expressed in the commonly used empirical Morison equation [18], which depicts motions and the hydrodynamic force on a cylinder as the sum of a drag force and the force due to acceleration of the fluid flowing around the cylinder. The lift force F_y is perpendicular to the wave motion, caused by vortex shedding on the downstream side of the riser. Vortices shed alternately from one side of the cylinder and then the other, resulting in a lateral oscillating force. The frequency of vortex shedding, f_s , is related to the riser diameter and flow velocity by the Strouhal number [18]. Both the Strouhal number S and the lift coefficient C_L are functions of the Reynolds number. It is well recognized that when the vortex-shedding frequency approaches to the natural frequency of the riser string, the vortex

shedding tends to adjust to the vibration frequency of the riser, causing significant transverse oscillation, i.e., lock-in. The instantaneous vortex shedding frequency is

$$f_s = \begin{cases} f_n & \text{(Lock - in)} \\ \frac{S|u|}{D} & \text{(Otherwise)} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where f_n is the natural frequency of the composite riser. The lock-in occurs when the reduced velocity, $\frac{U}{f_n D}$, reaches a value between 4 and 8 [18].

3. COMPUTATIONAL MECHANICS MODELS AND ALGORITHM

Governing equations for the composite riser dynamics with the aforementioned viscoelastic material constitutive properties subject to the fluid-motion-induced forces are highly nonlinear. The exact solution for the problem is difficult to obtain in general. However, approximate solutions may be obtained with the aid of suitable numerical (e. g., finite element) methods.

In this study, hollow composite-cylinder elements are used to model dynamic motions of long composite riser joints (riser string). The element formulation is based on the well-known Timoshenko beam theory to allow transverse shear deformations. The metal-composite-interface (MCI) connection is modeled as a mass element in this study.

The forces caused by vortex shedding are introduced as element nodal forces by employing a user-developed element subroutine (UEL) to account for the vortex-induced loading. Hydrodynamic force (via the Morrison Equation), inertia force and buoyancy load may be conveniently introduced by using the available numerical algorithms. With the aid of the ABQUS/Aqua [19], current profiles and wave conditions for the composite risers can be easily included in the computational algorithm of the structural dynamics formulation.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Composite Production Riser Geometry, Lamination Parameters and Material Properties -

Consider the composite production riser (CPR), which has been investigated in Ref. [3] for use in a 3,000-ft tension-leg platform system. The composite riser cylinder has an inner-diameter of 10.05” with a 62-ft length in each joint. The CPR construction makes use of filament-wound hybrid fiber/epoxy composite laminates, in which its axial load is carried mainly by the ($\pm 10^\circ$) helical carbon fibers and the pressure load is taken mostly by ($\pm 80^\circ$) hoop carbon/epoxy and E-glass/epoxy layers. Details of the composite lamination parameters and constituent material systems for the riser body are given in Refs. [3, 4].

The inner liners considered here are a brittle epoxy, a thermoplastic Kynar and a high damping epoxy. The time-dependent, anisotropic viscoelastic behavior of individual composite material systems with different viscoelastic epoxy matrices for the composite riser construction has been expressed in the form of a Prony series (Eq. 1). The stress-relaxation viscoelastic moduli of different resin matrices and liners in a time domain are obtained by a Fourier transform and shown in Fig. 2

Fig. 2. Viscoelastic Relaxation Moduli $G(t)/G_0$ for Different Resin Matrices and Liners ($T=25^\circ\text{C}$).

4.2 Current, Wave and Other Loading on Composite Risers - Numerical simulations of the dynamic response of the composite riser subject to combined current and wave loading have been conducted with the aid of the ABAQUS software and the aforementioned user-implemented subroutine to include the vortex-induced loading. The wave and current profiles, riser weight and dimensions, and the applied top-tension loading used in the dynamic analysis of the composite riser are given in Table 1. The top tension introduced for the composite riser string is about two times of the riser weight in water as suggested in [20].

Table 1. Assumed Loading for VIV Analysis of Composite Production Riser

Composite Riser Joint Length	62	Feet
ID	10.05	Inch
OD	12.058	Inch
MCI Weight	341	Lb
Riser String Length	3038	Feet
Water Depth	3038	Feet
Top Tension	75	Kips
Current at Surface	2.5	Feet/Sec
Current at Bottom	0	Feet/Sec
Wave Height (Peak to Trough)	20	Feet
Wave Period	9	Second
Content in Riser	Water	

4.3 Effect of Various Resin Matrices on Composite Riser Dynamics - It is noted that fluid damping appears to be the dominant dissipative mechanism for riser VIV. The overall displacement profile of the rigid composite riser is larger than that of a similar steel riser since the composite riser has a lower lateral structural stiffness. However, in the previous study [15] on riser dynamics, the matrix material in the composite laminate and structural tailoring have been introduced to provide additional dissipation of the dynamic energy in the advanced composite riser design to meet specific performance requirements of riser vibration.

Also, the concept of reducing dynamic bending stress in a riser joint by increasing the resin material damping is demonstrated by conducting several analyses on the risers made of hybrid glass/epoxy and

carbon/epoxy plies with the aforementioned brittle structural epoxy and high-damping epoxy resins (Fig. 2). In the riser dynamics study, deformations and stresses in the composite riser under wave, current and VIV loading are commonly expressed with their mean and root-mean-square (RMS) values.

By increasing the composite resin matrix material damping, dynamic bending stresses are reduced in riser joints. For the case of brittle and high-damping epoxy resins used in riser laminate lay-ups ($\pm 80^\circ/\pm 10^\circ$), the RMS displacements caused by the current and vortex-induced vibration are shown in Figs. 3(a) and 3(b), respectively. The dynamic bending stresses in the composite risers are shown in Figs. 4(a) and 4(b), respectively. A significant amount of reduction in both the RMS displacement and stress is observed in the composite riser with a high-damping matrix. Near the stress joint at the seabed ($Z/L = 0$), more than 50% reduction in the riser bending stress is found. However, the effect of high matrix-material damping on the dynamic riser stress is found to be less significant near the surface ($Z/L = 1$), due to the high top tension applied.

Fig. 3(a). Effect of Different Resin Matrices on RMS Displacements Induced by Current and Waves in Composite Risers.

Fig. 3(b). Effect of Different Resin Matrices on RMS VIV Displacements in Composite Risers.

Fig. 4(a.) Effect of Different Riser Laminate Lay-ups and Resin Matrices on RMS Stress Induced by Current and Waves.

Fig. 4(b). Effect of Different Riser Laminate Lay-ups and Resin Matrices on RMS Vortex-Induced-Vibration (VIV) Stresses.

4.4 Effect of Laminate Lay-up on Composite Riser Dynamics - The effect of composite riser laminate stacking sequence on composite riser VIV has been studied by considering the hoop layers with various fiber angles ($\pm\theta^\circ$), i. e., ($\pm 80^\circ$), ($\pm 75^\circ$), ($\pm 65^\circ$) and ($\pm 55^\circ$), and the helical carbon fibers with two set of angles, i. e., ($\pm 10^\circ$) and ($\pm 15^\circ$) [For the convenience of discussion, thus, the composite riser laminate lay-up system is expressed as ($\pm\theta^\circ/\pm 10^\circ$) or ($\pm\theta^\circ/\pm 15^\circ$)]. For the risers with a brittle epoxy resin, the dynamic bending stresses caused by current and vortex-induced vibrations at different riser depths are given in Figs. 5(a) and 5(b). The RMS bending stresses are reduced (in both VIV and current/waves motions), as the hoop angle θ or the helical carbon-fiber angle increase.

Fig. 5(a). Effect of Different Laminate Lay-ups on RMS Stress (induced by current and waves) at Different Z/L Along the Composite Risers.

Fig. 5(b). Effect of Different Laminate Lay-ups on RMS Stress (VIV) at Different Z/L Along the Composite Risers.

4.5 Effect of Liner Materials on Composite Riser Dynamics – The effects of liner material and its thickness on composite riser dynamics are studied. The frequencies and modes of the composite riser vibration with several liner thicknesses are given in Table 2. By adding an inner liner to the riser body structure, the natural frequency of the riser, hence the lock-in vortex shedding frequency, are changed.

For the risers with different laminate lay-ups ($\pm\theta^\circ/\pm 10^\circ$), the RMS stresses at water depth $Z/L=0.96$ are shown in Figs. 6(a) and 6(b). The dynamic RMS stresses are reduced significantly with the liner made of a high-damping resin. Also, the RMS bending stresses in the risers decrease while the hoop angle θ and liner thickness increase.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The effects of resin matrix material and lamination lay-up parameters on vortex-induced vibration of deepwater composite risers have been studied. Dynamic riser deformation and stress can be significantly reduced by increasing the resin material damping. Detailed dynamic analyses of VIV have been conducted on the composite risers made of hybrid glass/epoxy and carbon/epoxy plies with brittle structural epoxy and high-damping epoxy resins. In the riser VIV analysis, time-dependent composite material properties with resin-matrix damping has been introduced to formulate the shell structural stiffness in the riser dynamic motion equations under current and wave-induced loading. The vortex-induced RMS displacements in the risers are found to be reduced by the high-damping resin matrix material. Also, a significant amount of decrease in the RMS stresses is observed in the composite risers containing a high-damping matrix material. The effects of composite riser laminate stacking sequence on composite riser dynamics have been evaluated by considering the hoop layers with various fiber

orientations ($\pm\theta^\circ$) and the helical carbon fibers with two set angles, i. e., ($\pm 10^\circ$) and ($\pm 15^\circ$). The RMS bending stresses are found to be appreciably reduced as the hoop angle θ or the helical carbon-fiber angle increase. The effect of polymer liners with different resin materials and thicknesses on the VIV dynamic response has been studied. The structural frequencies, vibration modes, and RMS displacements and stresses in the composite riser are all affected significantly due to increasing liner material damping and thickness. The magnitude of the VIV stress reduction caused by adding a polymer liner is larger than that by introducing an effective damping matrix only in the composite riser body construction.

Table 2. Frequencies and Modes of Composite Risers with Different Liner Materials

Mode No.	Frequency (Hz) (without liner)	Frequency (Hz) Brittle Epoxy Liner, (t= 0.5 inch)	Frequency (Hz) Kynar Liner, (t= 0.5 inch)
1	0.056939	0.049153	0.049151
2	0.056946	0.049159	0.049158
3	0.11404	0.098446	0.098442
4	0.11404	0.098448	0.098444
5	0.17103	0.14764	0.14763
6	0.17103	0.14765	0.14764
7	0.22791	0.19675	0.19673
8	0.22791	0.19675	0.19673
9	0.28466	0.24574	0.24571
10	0.28466	0.24574	0.24571
11	0.34124	0.29458	0.29454
12	0.34124	0.29458	0.29454
13	0.39762	0.34326	0.34319
14	0.39762	0.34326	0.34319
15	0.45378	0.39174	0.39164
16	0.45378	0.39174	0.39164
17	0.50967	0.44000	0.43986
18	0.50968	0.44000	0.43986
19	0.56528	0.48802	0.48783
20	0.56528	0.48802	0.48783
21	0.62057	0.53576	0.53551
22	0.62058	0.53576	0.53551
23	0.67552	0.58321	0.58289
24	0.67552	0.58321	0.58289
25	0.68865	0.60624	0.59303

Fig. 6(a). Combined Effect of Composite Laminate Lay-up, Liner Material and Thickness on RMS Stress (Induced by Current and Waves) in Composite Risers ($Z/L = 0.96$).

Fig. 6(b). Combined Effect of Composite Laminate Lay-up, Liner Material and Thickness on RMS Stress (VIV) in Composite Risers ($Z/L = 0.96$).

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